

NEW INTERACTIVE METHODS FOR TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE TO YOUNG LEARNERS AT CLASSROOM

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ABSTRACT

In today's developing world, the demand for technologies, robototechnics and science is growing along with learning foreign languages, mainly English. In fact, English is considered to be the most spoken language in the world and there are 58 countries where it is official language (USA, UK, Canada). Many of users involve youngsters from all the world, especially preschoolers from the age of 7-10 years old are more likely to learn English in their early childhood. In this article, designing the lesson in captivating way and teaching English as a foreign language by using new interactive methods at school.

INTRODUCTION: Preschoolers have well-developed memories and when new knowledge is given to them, they tend to remember it without losing what they have learned and use it effectively. In addition, in this time, they have mechanical memory, causing to memorize things automatically without understanding its exact meaning. However, they are more likely to get distracted or bored easily in the classroom. In this case, it is best way to use new technologies and interactive methods to conduct lesson more interesting way. Additionally, many of them wasting their time on Youtube and other internet platforms by taking their family members' phones, resulting serious health problems, mainly associated with eyesight and short attention span. If the usage of new interactive methods are expands, it helps to organize a lesson in interesting way, resulting to learn foreign languages faster among pre-schoolers and they will not be attracted by various types of gadgets, instead, elementary books in that language or electronic video tutorials.

1. Communicative language teaching (CLT) – this is a kind of approach which focuses on real-life communication like role-playing, group discussions and make up stories. For example, at first children learn new words about colors and then they will ask colour of items or clothes from each other as a dialogue or make up sentences using new vocabulary. It helps them keep it in long-term memory.

2. Total Physical Response- this is a kind of teaching method developed by psychologist Dr. James, J. Asher in the last century. It emphasizes on real – life actions, mainly verbs. To be precise, when children learn new verbs, they should act out them, like, "Jump", run, clap and do it in real life, helping them to learn it effectively and full of fun

3. Multiple intelligences theory- this approach focuses on different types of handouts at the same time, in order to conduct a lesson in captivating way and engage more students rather than using ordinary handouts. This approach includes audio, visual, hand gestures or mimics to teach a vocabulary. For example when teaching fruits and vegetables, it is best way to show pictures of them to children. In addition, listening different sounds made by animals, aids children to differentiate animals by only hearing, it is full of fun for them. Moreover, using music while explaining the meaning of new words, makes learning easier for youngsters, because they will repeat after the music. For example, when teacher show the musical video about weekdays, children will repeat consistently with it together.

4. Game based learning – this approach is about games which are related to theme, like hot potato, Simon says, cha cha according to pre-schoolers age and their theme. These following methods makes the lesson a bit interesting and helps teachers to create friendly learning atmosphere among children, I also used some of them while doing practicum at school. Firstly, hot potato is the way for revising last topics or words, teacher take sheet of paper and write some questions about new vocabulary and wrap it to some fruits like apple, orange, and teacher should throw this round object to children saying “hot potato”, if children take this potato, at first he or she should answer the question and keep potato as a prize. The next approach names Simon says- teacher give commands like” Simon touch your nose, hair or Simon touch yellow colour, if teacher don’t say the word Simon, and only say touch”, children should not do this, just stay still, if the children make a movement, they will lose a game. This method helps children to make longer their attention span level and differentiate key phrases.

5. Picture brain-storming –in this method, teacher will show a picture of zoo, house, garden, playground, school and ask a question, what we can do here”. This approach is also known from **Soft Systems Methodology** (SSM) which were famous last 1970s. This makes learning fun and improves critical thinking from a young age among children. They will use new vocabularies, their imagination and be confident while explaining their opinions.

CONCLUSION. Psychologist A.P. Usova clearly shows the level of mastery of lessons by preschool children. That is, she distinguishes three types of mastery of lessons in children. The first level is when a child is interested in learning, active in lessons, and able to control his actions, and the indicators of mastery of new lessons are relatively weak. In the third type, the stage of development of children's organizational disciplines in educational activities. According to the famous German psychologist O. Kron, children are able to master the knowledge given to them from the age of three, that is, to acquire knowledge. These are the three years, the new three years, or the child receives knowledge not according to the plans and programs drawn up by his parents' educators, but according to his own program. The main thing is to adapt to the plans created by the child's educators and receive knowledge according to this program. Thus, we can see a number of modern methods for making a child interested in learning, that is, teaching languages to children in an easy and understandable, but at the same time hidden way.

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